

Phytochemical Investigation of *Parthenium hysterophorous* Linn. An Irritating but Promising Weed

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PARTHENIUM hysterophorous Linn. (Compositae), though native to West Indies and Central and Northern America now grows abundantly throughout India. The plant is well known for its irritant properties and dermatitis causing effect. In spite of these, *Parthenium* possesses a number of useful properties. It is reported to be used as a powerful tonic, febrifuge, analgesic in neuralgia, in dysentery and as an agent to stimulate menstrual function¹. An active principle, parthenin², isolated previously from this plant is reported to have anti-cancer properties. Moreover, the plant is highly resistant to all pathogens and insect predators¹.

Petroleum ether extract of dried and powdered whole plant, followed by careful separation through chromatography over silica gel afforded compound A and a sterol, C₂₉H₄₈O, m.p. 155-56°, identified as stigmasterol.

Compound A, C₁₆H₃₂O (M⁺, 240), m.p. 80°, showed characteristic ir absorption bands at 1750 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) and 733, 722 cm⁻¹. Characteristic doublet at 1481 and 1471 cm⁻¹ coupled with the presence of strong peak at m/z 43 in its mass spectrum suggested the presence of *iso*-propyl group in the molecule. Besides the broad signal at δ 1.20 and a triplet around δ 0.90 (3H), the other important characteristic pmr signal is around δ 2.26 (4H, m). Mass spectra of the compound showed besides molecular ion peak at m/z 240 a number of prominent peaks at m/z 43, 57 (base peak), 72, 85, 98, 113 and 127 which can be rationalised fairly well on the basis of the structure (I)

The marc left after the light petroleum ether extract was extracted with chloroform. The concentrate upon chromatographic purification yielded a further crop of stigmasterol from benzene eluate. Further elution with chloroform furnished a compound, C₁₅H₁₈O₄ (M⁺, 262), m.p. 164-66°, identified as parthenin² (m.m.p., co-tlc and mixed ir).

Experimental

All melting points were recorded on a Kofler Block and are uncorrected. The air dried and powdered whole plant (2.50 kg) of *Parthenium hysterophorous* was exhaustively extracted with light petrol (60-80°) in a soxhlet for 24 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the crude blackish residue (20 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (450 g) using solvents of increasing polarity as eluents. Light petrol (60-80°)-benzene (3 : 1) eluates afforded compound A, which was crystallised from acetone as granular white solid, C₁₆H₃₂O (M⁺, 240), m.p. 80°. (Found : C, 79.8 ; H, 12.9. C₁₆H₃₂O requires C, 80.0 ; H, 13.3%).

Benzene eluates yielded white crystalline substance, m.p. 155-56° which was identified as stigmasterol.

The marc left after light petrol extract was then exhaustively extracted with benzene. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel when a further crop of stigmasterol migrated out with benzene. Chloroform fractions yielded white semi solid residue (0.70 g) which upon rechromatography over silica gel furnished white solid which was crystallised from light petrol-benzene mixture as needles. The compound, C₁₅H₁₈O₄ (M⁺, 262), m.p. 164-65° was identified as parthenin². (Found : C, 68.54 ; H, 6.70. C₁₅H₁₈O₄ requires C, 68.70 ; H, 6.83%).

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Chemical Examination of *Scirpus tuberosus* (Cyperaceae)†

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MEDICINAL uses attributed to several members of the natural order Cyperaceae^{1,2} attracted our attention to *Scirpus tuberosus*, an aquatic plant

† Full details of the isolation and identification of the compounds are available on request.

which grows abundantly around Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh. In this communication we report the isolation and identification of β -sitosterol and two triterpenoids from the roots of this plant which has not been chemically investigated previously.

The plant material was collected locally during the monsoon. The dried roots, cut into small pieces, were extracted successively with petroleum ether and alcohol. The petroleum ether extract was adsorbed on a column of silica gel and the column eluted with petrol-benzene (3 : 1) and benzene. The compounds obtained from the eluate were purified by rechromatography and crystallisation to afford β -sitosterol (m.p. 131-32°) and betulin (m.p. 252-54°), respectively. The alcoholic extract on concentration deposited a solid, which was purified by chromatography on silica gel and identified as betulinic acid. The isolated compounds were identified on the basis of spectral data (nmr and ir) and comparison with authentic samples^{3,4} (m.m.p.). Derivatives of the isolated compounds prepared for their identification included β -sitosterol acetate and benzoate, betulin acetate (m.p. 220°), betulinic acid acetate (m.p. 289°) and methyl ester of betulinic acid acetate (m.p. 198°).

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Chemical Investigation of *Mollugo pentaphylla*

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MOLLUGO pentaphylla, one of the three species of the genus *Mollugo* (fam. Molluginaceae) is an annual shrub and grows in paddy and maize fields during July-August. The other two species are *Mollugo spargula* (grows at the base of the eastern Himalayas²) and *Mollugo hirta* (distributed in West Bengal³).

*Mollugo spargula*³⁻⁵ and *Mollugo hirta*⁹⁻¹³ were studied in detail for their chemical constituents.

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Literature reveals that *Mollugo pentaphylla* has not been studied chemically so far. Jha *et al*^{1,4} reported the crude methanolic extract of this plant to possess spermistatic activity and Chopra^{1,5} described other medicinal uses of this plant. Hence a chemical investigation of the aerial part of this plant was undertaken. All known compounds were characterised by comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic samples.

Finely powdered plant material (1 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in soxhlet apparatus followed by extraction with methanol.

Petroleum ether extract :

The plant extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a semisolid mass, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina.

Alkanes : Elution of the column with hexane yielded a white waxy solid, m.p. 68-70° (acetone). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$: 2950, 2870, 1470, 1399, 725 and 715 cm^{-1} .

Gas chromatographic analysis of the above solid on Pye-Unicam gas chromatograph (model 124) (dual glass column 2.5 m x 3 mm, f.i.d., adsorbent 3% SE-30 on Chrom-2, programmed at 350° with 4°/min, carrier gas N₂ at 45 ml/min, chart speed 15"/hr) gave the following alkanes (percentage within parentheses) : C₁₈(36.03), C₁₉(1.71), C₂₀(15.44), C₂₁(1.38), C₂₂(0.85), C₂₃(3.44), C₂₄(0.36), C₂₅(1.71), C₂₆(5.15), *iso*-C₁₈(17.11), *iso*-C₂₂(1.71), *iso*-C₂₃(1.37), *iso*-C₂₅(5.15) and *iso*-C₂₆(8.58). Authentic samples (Analabs, USA) were co-chromatographed under identical conditions and identifications were made according to Hardman, Wood and Sofowora¹⁶.

β -Sitosterol : Elution (petroleum ether-benzene ; 1 : 4) yielded β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-38°, acetate : m.p. 125-26°.

Methanolic extract :

The defatted plant material was next extracted with methanol in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract was concentrated to a sticky mass under reduced pressure which gave copious honey comb foam with water. It was dissolved in minimum volume of methanol and purified by repeated precipitation by pouring into large volume of acetone. The crude yellow saponin was resolved into five spots on silica gel G layers (solvent : I, di-isopropyl ether ; II, methylene chloride, hR_f 20, 41, 62, 85 and 93) and was also separated by preparative tlc (silica gel G, chloroform-methanol ; 95 : 5).

Oleanolic acid : (hR_f 41). Colourless needles, m.p. 303-304°, acetate, m.p. 262-63°.

Mollugogenol A : (hR_f 62). Colourless needles, m.p. 248-50°, acetate, m.p. 227-30°.

Mollugogenol B : (hR_f 85). Colourless needles, m.p. 220-23°; acetate, m.p. 192-94°.

Mollugogenol D : (hR_f 93). Colourless needles, m.p. 281-88° dec, acetate, m.p. 264-66°.

L-Rhamnopyranosyl-D-glucopyranosyl mollugogenol A : (hR_f 20). It gave the usual tests for a